

The Photochemical Reduction of Methyl Red by Phenylhydrazine using Chlorophyll Solution as Photosensitiser.

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BöHi (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1929 **12**, 121) found that a large number of azo-dyes are reduced by exposure to light in presence of chlorophyll in methyl alcohol solution. The chlorophyll itself is destroyed but this can be prevented by adding one of the following anodic depolarisers: oil of turpentine, piperidine and phenylhydrazine. Addition of the last named compound was found to produce the most rapid photolysis. BöHi did not make any quantitative study and his experimental investigations were based on the theoretical views advanced by Baur (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1928, **34**, 595).

Thus, when the dyestuffs are decolourised by exposure to light and in presence of chlorophyll, the mechanism is as follows:—

and in presence of anodic depolariser, such as phenylhydrazine, the reaction takes place in the following way:

In this paper, the reduction of the azo-dye, methyl red has been studied in the monochromatic radiations 4358 $\overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$ and 5460 $\overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$.

The paper is divided in four sections. The first section (Sec. A) deals with the reduction of the dyestuff in methyl alcohol solution at 4358 $\overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$. In Sec. B, the same reaction was studied in benzene solution at 4358 $\overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$. The reaction at 5460 $\overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$ both in alcohol and benzene

solution, is given in Sec. C. In Sec. D, the reduction of dyestuff by phenylhydrazine hydrochloride is given.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The amount of methyl red reduced was determined by König Marten spectrophotometer. In green region, the methyl red solution obeys Beer's Law. A small rectangular glass cell containing known strength of methyl red solutions in methyl alcohol was placed in spectrometer table and the angles in the disc which gave fields of equal illumination were found out for four or five dilutions. By plotting values of $\log \tan \theta_2 - \log \tan \theta_1$ against the concentration, a straight line was obtained. θ_2 and θ_1 are the final and initial angles respectively. When mixtures of chlorophyll and methyl red were used, a solution of chlorophyll alone of the same concentration was kept in the compensation cell. From the straight line thus obtained the concentrations of methyl red corresponding to any angle could be interpolated easily.

The light source was a point-o-lite mercury arc lamp run from a storage battery of 28 volts and maintained at a constant current of 2.2 amperes. Convex lenses of various focal length placed at a distance from the lamp equal to their focal lengths gave parallel beams of light of different intensities. The reaction vessel $1.55 \times 1.55 \times 0.8$ cm. was made of plane parallel glass sides with a stopper at the top and was placed inside a double jacketed metal box with a plane glass window on one side to admit light. By continuous circulation of water through the annular space in the box from a thermostat by means of a pump, the temperature was maintained constant. Zeiss monochromatic filters which transmit only the radiations of wave-lengths 5460\AA and 4358\AA in combination with 1 cm. thick dilute copper sulphate solutions were used for green and blue light respectively.

Mercks' indicator methyl red and reagent methanol (free from acetone) were used throughout the experiment. Kahlbaum's reagent phenylhydrazine was purified and stored in the dark in vacuum.

Each reaction is characterised by a long induction period, depending on the strength of oxidant and reductant and intensity of incident light. Generally, it was observed that the induction period decreased with decrease in the concentration of methyl red and increased concentration of phenylhydrazine,

Section A.

TABLE Ia.

Wave-length = 4358Å. Solvent = Methyl alcohol. Temp = 25°.

Intensity of radiation absorbed by a solution having initial concentrations $M/10,000$ -methyl red, $M/20,000$ -chlorophyll, $M/200$ -phenylhydrazine is 196 ergs ; t represents any arbitrary time after the induction period is over.

Time in min.	Conc. of methyl red.	K (zero mol.).
$t + 0$	8.1×10^{-5}	0.06×10^{-5}
$t + 30$	6.3	0.058
$t + 70$	4.0	

TABLE Ib.

	$t + 0$	$t + 30$	$t + 75$	$t + 125$	$t + 175$
$3M/20,000$ -methyl red ...					
$M/20,000$ -chlorophyll ...	15×10^{-5}	13.2×10^{-5}	10.5×10^{-5}	7.5×10^{-5}	4.5×10^{-5}
$M/200$ -phenylhydrazine ...	0.06×10^{-5}	0.06×10^{-5}	0.06×10^{-5}	0.06×10^{-5}	...

The reaction is thus a zero molecular one, equal quantities being converted in equal times, independent of the concentration of methyl red.

Influence of variation of concentration of phenylhydrazine on the velocity of reaction.

TABLE II.

The conditions of experiment are the same as in Table Ia.

Conc. of phenylhydrazine (mols) ...	0.02	0.01	0.005
$K \times 10^5$...	0.055	0.056	0.06

The velocity of reaction is practically independent of concentration of phenylhydrazine.

Influence of concentrations of chlorophyll on the velocity of reaction.

TABLE III.

Intensity of incident radiation = 124 ergs. Initial concentration of the mixture = $M/10,000$ -methyl red and $M/200$ -phenylhydrazine.

Conc. of chlorophyll $\times 10^5$...	1.66	2.5	5	10
$K \times 10^5$...	0.023	0.027	0.03	0.027

The velocity of reaction passes through a maximum as the concentration of chlorophyll is increased. It has been observed by us that the fluorescent power of chlorophyll also passes through maximum at the same concentration.

Temperature coefficient of the velocity of reaction.—This has been found to be practically unity. The velocity of reaction is independent of temperature within the range of 23° to 35°.

Influence of the state of polarisation of incident radiation.—It has been found that the state of polarisation is without any effect on the velocity of reaction.

Calculation of quantum efficiency.—The energy of radiation was measured by a Moll thermopile and a Moll galvanometer. Radiant energy from a Hefner lamp at a distance of 1 metre from the thermopile whose intensity is equal to 900 ergs produced a deflection of 41 divisions. The light absorbed by a solution 0.8 cm. thick having the composition— $M/10,000$ -methyl red, $M/20,000$ -chlorophyll, $M/200$ -phenylhydrazine is equivalent to 9 divisions of the galvanometer. Total number of quanta absorbed by the solution exposing a surface of 2.4 sq. cm. = 104×10^{12} ($\lambda = 4358\text{\AA}$).

The change in concentration of methyl red in 30 minutes = 1.8×10^{-5} (*vide* Table I a). The volume of reaction vessel = 2.4×0.8 c.c.

Hence the quantum efficiency $\gamma = 0.13$ approximately.

If however we take into account only the fraction of radiant energy which is absorbed by chlorophyll only, we obtain a much higher quantum yield. Methyl red and phenylhydrazine exposed to blue radiation in absence of chlorophyll does not react with each other. Hence it is clear that the radiant energy absorbed by chlorophyll only is effective. We can as a rough approximation assume that the radiant energy absorbed by chlorophyll molecules in presence of methyl red is given by,

$$I_f = I_a \frac{\epsilon_{chl} C_{chl}}{\epsilon_{chl} C_{chl} + \epsilon_{meR} C_{meR}}$$

where I_a represents the total energy absorbed, ϵ_{chl} , C_{chl} , ϵ_{meR} , C_{meR} represents the molar extinction coefficients and concentrations of chlorophyll and methyl red.

For $\lambda = 4358\text{\AA}$, $E_{chl} = 17,000$ and $\epsilon_{meR} = 21,000$.

Hence the factor $\frac{\epsilon_{chl} C_{chl}}{\epsilon_{chl} C_{chl} + \epsilon_{meR} C_{meR}}$ has the value $1/3.4$ approximately.

And the real quantum efficiency $\gamma=0.45$.

The quantum efficiencies for the experimental data recorded in Table III has been calculated in this way and the results are recorded below.

TABLE IV.

Conc. of chlorophyll $\times 10^5$...	1.66	2.5	5	10
γ ...	1.08	0.8	0.45	0.2

Section B.

Dark reaction.—The dark reaction is extremely slow. No change in the concentration of methyl red was observed in 6 hours. A solution containing methyl red, phenylhydrazine and chlorophyll kept in the dark for 20 hours showed only 5 % reduction of methyl red. Hence the velocity of dark reaction can be neglected.

TABLE V.

Intensity of absorbed radiation is 130 ergs when the solution has the following composition : $M/10,000$ -methyl red, $M/20,000$ -chlorophyll, $M/50$ -phenylhydrazine. $\lambda = 4358 \text{ \AA}$. Temp. = 25° .

Solvent = Benzene.

Time in min.	Conc. of methyl red $\times 10^5$.	$-\frac{1}{C_0} \cdot \frac{dc}{dt} = K$.
$t+0$	4.74	0.0014
$t+120$	4.0	
$t+0$	2.64	
$t+120$	2.24	0.0013

The reaction velocity is too slow to be followed to completion. The agreement between the values of unimolecular constants for different initial concentration of methyl red is, however, quite good.

Effect of varying concentrations of phenylhydrazine.

TABLE VI.

$M/10,000$ -Methyl red.	$M/20,000$ -Chlorophyll.		
Conc. (mols/litre) of phenylhydrazine ...	0.04	0.02	0.01
$K = -\frac{1}{C_0} \cdot \frac{dc}{dt}$...	0.0028	0.0014	0.0008

The unimolecular velocity constant with respect to methyl red is proportional to the concentration of phenylhydrazine.

Effect of varying concentration of chlorophyll.

TABLE VII.

<i>M</i> /10,000-Methyl red.		<i>M</i> /25-Phenylhydrazine.		
Conc. of chlorophyll $\times 10^5$... 1.66	5	10	
<i>K</i>	... 0.002	0.0028	0.0025	

As in the case of methyl alcohol as solvent, the velocity constant is a maximum at the concentration of 5×10^{-5} .

Temperature coefficient.—Temperature has no influence on the velocity constant.

Quantum efficiency.—The quantum efficiency can be calculated from the first data in Table V. 0.74×10^{-5} g. molecules of methyl red represent the change in concentration in 120 minutes; the total volume of the solution = 2.4×0.8 c.c. The number of quanta absorbed by the solution per second was found to be 70×10^{12} . The number of molecules transformed per sec. = 1.2×10^{12} . The quantum efficiency $\gamma = 0.017$.

If we take into consideration the radiation absorbed by chlorophyll only, γ has the value of 0.05 approximately.

$$\epsilon_{chl} = 17,500 \text{ and } \epsilon_{MeR} = 17,000.$$

Section C.

TABLE VIIIa.

Solvent = Alcohol. Temp. = 25° . Incident intensity = 3000 ergs.
M/5,000-Methyl red. *M*/25-Phenylhydrazine. *M*/20,000-Chlorophyll.

Time in min.	... <i>t</i> + 0	<i>t</i> + 25	<i>t</i> + 45	<i>t</i> + 65
Conc. of methyl red $\times 10^5$... 17.46	13.26	9.62	6.0
<i>K</i> (zero) $\times 10^5$... —	0.17	0.18	0.18

TABLE VIIIb.

Solvent = Benzene. Incident intensity = 1400 ergs. Other conditions same as in Table VIIIa.

Time in min.	... <i>t</i> + 0	<i>t</i> + 30	<i>t</i> + 90
Conc. of methyl red $\times 10^5$... 11.3	9.5	6.0
<i>K</i> $\times 10^5$ (zero mol.)	... —	0.06	0.059

TABLE VIIIc.

Conditions same as in Table VIIIb, only the initial concentration of methyl red was less.

Time in min. ...	$t+0$	$t+30$	$t+50$
Conc of methyl red $\times 10^5$	5.8	3.9	2.6
$K \times 10^5$ (zero mol.) ...	—	0.063	0.065

The reaction in both solvents is thus a zero molecular one.

Effect of variation in the concentration of phenylhydrazine in methyl alcohol solution.

TABLE IX.

Conditions same as in Table VIIIa.

Conc. (mols/litre) of phenylhydrazine ...	0.04	0.01	0.005
$K \times 10^5$...	0.17	0.18	0.17

The velocity constant is practically independent of the concentration of phenylhydrazine.

Influence of concentration of chlorophyll on velocity constant.

TABLE X.

Incident intensity = 1400 ergs. $M/10,000$ -Methyl red.
 $M/25$ -Phenylhydrazine.

Methyl alcohol.		Benzene.	
Conc. of chlorophyll $\times 10^5$.	$K \times 10^5$.	Conc. of chlorophyll $\times 10^5$.	$K \times 10^5$.
1.2	0.06	1.66	0.036
2.5	0.077	2.5	0.062
5	0.074	5	0.06
10	0.06	10	0.048

In both these solvents the velocity constant passes through a maximum when the chlorophyll concentration is approximately 2.5×10^5 .

Temperature has no influence on the velocity of reaction.

Quantum efficiency.—In both the solvents, the velocity of reaction was found to be proportional to the intensity of incident radiation.

The extinction coefficients for methyl red and chlorophyll in benzene solution for radiation $\lambda = 5460\text{\AA}$ are 900 and 1500 respectively. On the assumption that the radiant energy is absorbed by each species of molecules as if the other is not present, we obtain

$$I_{\text{abs}} = I_0 \left[1 - e^{-\epsilon_{\text{chl}} C_{\text{chl}}} - e^{-\epsilon_{\text{meR}} C_{\text{meR}}} \right]$$

For $C_{\text{chl}} = 5 \times 10^{-5}$ and $C_{\text{meR}} = 5.8 \times 10^{-5}$, I_{abs} has value $1400 \times 0.105 = 147$ ergs. approximately. This agrees well with the value of light absorbed as measured directly by Moll thermopile and galvanometer.

Hence, we are justified in assuming that the light absorbed by chlorophyll only is given by the equation,

$$I = I_0 \left[1 - e^{-\epsilon_{\text{chl}} C_{\text{chl}}} \right]$$

In Table VIIIc, light absorbed by chlorophyll alone is 84 ergs. approximately per sq. cm.

$$\text{Total quantum absorbed per } 2.4 \text{ sq. cm.} = \frac{84 \times 2.4}{3.6 \times 10^{-12}}$$

Total number of molecules transformed per sec.

$$= \frac{2.4 \times 0.8 \times 0.065 \times 10^{-5} \times 6.16 \times 10^{23}}{60 \times 1000}$$

$\gamma = 0.24$ approximately. ϵ for chlorophyll in methyl alcohol solution = 1600.

The experimental data in Table X have been used to calculate quantum efficiency and the values of γ are recorded below.

TABLE XI.

Methyl alcohol.		Benzene.	
Conc. of chlorophyll $\times 10^5$.	γ .	Conc. of chlorophyll $\times 10^5$.	γ .
1.2	1.0	1.66	0.45
2.5	0.70	2.5	0.48
5	0.32	5	0.24
10	0.13	10	0.10

Section D.

If phenylhydrazine is replaced by phenylhydrazine hydrochloride, the results obtained are materially different. The dark reaction proceeds very slowly though with measurable speed. The dark reaction is found to be unimolecular with respect to each of the reactants.

TABLE XIIa.

Solvent = Methyl alcohol. Temp. = 30°. Light absorbed by initial reaction mixture at $\lambda = 4358\text{\AA} = 265$ ergs. $M/40,000$ -Chlorophyll. $M/250$ -Phenylhydrazine hydrochloride.

Time in min.	Conc. of methyl red $\times 10^5$.	K (uni mol.).
0	5	Induction period.
185	4	
195	3.35	0.00126
285	2.61	0.00128
305	1.86	0.00129

The velocity of the corresponding dark reaction is given below. The dark reaction has an induction period of about 3 hrs.

TABLE XIIb.

Time in min.	...	180	300	420
Conc. of methyl red $\times 10^5$...	5	4.6	4.4
K	...	0.00023		0.00023

Effect of varying concentration of phenylhydrazine hydrochloride.

TABLE XIII.

$M/20,000$ -Methyl red. $M/40,000$ -Chlorophyll. The incident light same as in Table XIIa.

Conc. of phenylhydrazine hydrochloride.	K dark & light.	K dark.	K true light.
0.008 M	0.00155	0.0005	0.00105
0.004	0.00123	0.00025	0.00098
0.002	0.00098	0.00012	0.00086

The unimolecular velocity constant for dark reaction is proportional to the concentration of phenylhydrazine hydrochloride, but the velocity of the true light reaction increases slightly as the concentration of phenylhydrazine hydrochloride increases.

I/K plotted against I/C gives a straight line.

FIG. 1.

Effect of variation of concentration of chlorophyll.

TABLE XIV.

$M/20,000$ -Methyl red. $M/200$ -Phenylhydrazine hydrochloride.
Intensity of incident light same as in Table XIIa.

Conc. of chlorophyll.	K (light & dark).	K (dark).	K (true light).
2.5×10^{-5}	0.00120	0.00025	0.00095
10×10^{-5}	0.00140	0.00025	0.00115

The velocity of dark reaction is independent of concentration of chlorophyll, while that of the true light reaction increases slightly as the concentration of chlorophyll increased.

Influence of temperature.—The velocity constant of the dark reaction is approximately doubled by a rise of 10° in temperature while the influence of temperature on the true light reaction is small.

Quantum efficiency.—The quantum efficiency of the reaction is very low; if we take into consideration the whole of the light absorbed by the reaction mixture γ has a value approximately equal to 0.004 and this increases to 0.013 approximately if light absorbed

by chlorophyll alone is considered. Surface of the reaction cell = 4 sq cm. and the thickness = 0.25 cm.

Similar results were obtained when radiant energy of wave-length 5460 Å is used for bringing about a photochemical change.

TABLE XV.

Radiation absorbed by the solution having composition $M/20,000$ -methyl red, $M/40,000$ -chlorophyll, $M/250$ -phenylhydrazine hydrochloride = 520 ergs. Temp. = 30°. $\lambda = 5460$ Å

Time in min.	...	0	50	110	200	320
Conc. of methyl red $\times 10^5$...		5	4.5	3.85	3.0	2.1
K (dark & light)	} Induction period.		0.00113	0.00110	0.00116	
K (true light)			0.00090	0.00087	0.00093	

Effect of varying the concentration of phenylhydrazine hydrochloride.

TABLE XVI.

Other condition same as in Table XV.

Conc. (mols/litre) of phenylhydrazine hydrochloride	...	0.004	0.008	0.01
K (true light)	...	0.00085	0.0016	0.00195

The velocity of reaction is proportional to the concentration of phenylhydrazine hydrochloride.

Effect of varying the concentration of chlorophyll.

TABLE XVII.

Other condition same as in Table XV.

Conc. of chlorophyll $\times 10^6$...	2.5	5	10
K (true light)	...	0.00085	0.0014	0.0022

Effect of incident radiation on the reaction velocity.—The reaction velocity is found to be directly proportional to the incident intensity. Temperature coefficient is small.

Quantum efficiency.—For $\lambda = 5460\text{\AA}$ and solvent methyl alcohol containing phenylhydrazine hydrochloride, $\epsilon_{\text{chl}} = 1800$ and $\epsilon_{\text{meR}} = 7600$; in Table XV the total energy absorbed = 520 ergs per sec. per sq. cm.

The energy absorbed by chlorophyll alone equals to 60 ergs approximately. The change in the concentration of methyl red in the last 120 minutes in Table XIIa is 0.9×10^{-5} . The change due to light alone is 0.75×10^{-5} approximately.

Surface of the reaction cell is 4 sq. cm. and the thickness 0.25 cm.

Hence the quantum efficiency $\gamma = 0.009$. Since the reaction is unimolecular with respect to methyl red, calculation of quantum efficiency has not much significance except as an indication that it has a very low value.

DISCUSSION.

The following mechanism of photosensitisation by chlorophyll explains all the principal features of the reaction between methyl red and phenylhydrazine or phenylhydrazine hydrochloride.

On the basis of the commonly accepted principles, that for steady state, the rate of formation of an unstable intermediate product is equal to its rate of disappearance, we obtain for the velocity of formation of leuco methyl red, the following equation,

$$\frac{d[\text{meR}]}{dt} = \frac{h\nu \cdot K_2 [\text{meR}]}{K_1 + K_2 [\text{meR}]} \times \frac{K_4 [\text{Ph}]}{K_3 + K_4 [\text{Ph}]}$$

* meR, Ph, chl_(a), etc. are symbols for methyl red, phenylhydrazine and active chlorophyll, etc.

(1) If K_1 and K_3 are both small compared with $K_2[\text{meR}]$ and $K_4[\text{Ph}]$ respectively, *i.e.*, if the periods of the active chlorophyll molecule and of the intermediate complex of methyl red and active chlorophyll molecule are large, the equation becomes zero-molecular. Under such conditions obviously the quantum efficiency should be of the order of unity. This has been found to be the case with phenylhydrazine as reductant in green light both for methyl alcohol and benzene as solvents and for blue light only with methyl alcohol as solvent.

(2) If K_1 is large compared with $K_2[\text{meR}]$ and K_3 also large compared with $K_4[\text{Ph}]$, the reaction becomes unimolecular with respect to each of the reacting molecules of methyl red and phenylhydrazine. The quantum efficiency is necessarily very small. This is the case with phenylhydrazine as reductant with blue light in benzene solution.

(3) With phenylhydrazine hydrochloride as reductant, K_1 is always very large compared with $K_2[\text{meR}]$ and hence the quantum efficiency is very low, and the velocity is unimolecular with respect to methyl red. The reaction could only be studied in methyl alcohol solution. In green light also K_3 is large compared with $K_5[\text{PhHCl}]$, and the velocity is accordingly unimolecular with respect to phenylhydrazine hydrochloride. In blue light, however, K_3 and $K_5\text{Ph HCl}$ are of the same order of magnitude, and therefore we found that the inverse of the unimolecular velocity constants plotted against the inverse of the concentrations of phenylhydrazine hydrochloride is a straight line.

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Received November 13, 1933.

